

“Provisional hints for a contemporary criticality. Tafuri vs Koolhaas.”

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INTRO

“If Rockefeller Centre represented the most complete “disenchanted mountain” of the 1930’s, renovated Pittsburgh was the maximum example of the “disenchanted city” of the 1960’s. The capitalist city no longer hid its face beneath a romantic mask; no Mendelsohn would ever again photograph Pittsburgh as a mysterious forest; no Saarinen or Ferriss would be moved to “sing” its force. The “city without quality” created itself in Pittsburgh as the direct expression of the forces that actually manage it.”

Manfredo Tafuri, “The Disenchanted Mountain”, in “The American City”, pg 493.¹

“Corbett’s “solution” for New York’s traffic problem is the most blatant case of disingenuity in Manhattanism’s history. Pragmatism so distorted becomes pure poetry.

Not for a moment does the theorist intend to relieve congestion; his true ambition is to escalate it to such intensity that generates –as in a quantum leap- a completely new condition, where congestion becomes mysteriously positive.”

Rem Koolhaas, “Delirious New York”, pg 123.²

Tafuri and Koolhaas’ account of the metropolitan condition through the history of the skyscraper are particularly interesting when read side by side. Written approximately in the same period, they nevertheless convey very different understandings of the metropolitan condition and, most importantly, they build different platforms for contemporary architectural practice.

PARADIGM

If the confrontation of Tafuri and Koolhaas’ texts is interesting, it is because, although participating of a similar ethic horizon (that of the need of a critical thought), they operate from two separate and irreducible paradigms. Each author falls at a different side of the hinge that is ongoingly understood as the most relevant of the last decades: that of the deconstruction of the (however heterodox) Marxist alienation paradigm³. To put it in Jameson’s words, “the alienation of the subject is replaced by the fragmentation of the subject”⁴.

Such comparison becomes especially revealing when the authors’ opinions are understood as different responses from two intellectuals belonging to the first generation being raised in the regime of total modernity as instituted by World War II. For people born in the forties, modernity is the default condition: not a utopian or visionary project anymore, but plain reality.

Both Tafuri and Koolhaas’ main similitude and main difference play themselves out through the concept of critique. Although both authors coincide in the (ethical) need for a critical practice,

¹ Manfredo Tafuri, “The Disenchanted Mountain”, in “The American City”, MIT Press.

² Rem Koolhaas, “Delirious New York”, The Monacelli Press, New York 1978.

³ Cf. for example, the accounting of the Situationist International as the last European avant-garde and their hinge position with respect to what has later been called post-modernity in those terms. Santiago Lopez Petit, “Horror vacui” Ed. Siglo XXI, Madrid; and unpublished notes from the PhD programme “Subjectivitat i Individualisme”, at UB, Barcelona.

Needless to say, we are not referring here to a dismissal of Marxist thought as a whole, it being already irrevocably incorporated within contemporary structures of understanding and management of reality. We are mainly pointing out the critique to the Marxian-Hegelian dialectical understanding of history (and the temporality implied), insofar as they constitute the frames for relevant action:

“Our age, whether through logic or epistemology, whether through Marx or through Nietzsche, is attempting to flee Hegel.” Michel Foucault “Orders of Discourse”, in “Social Science Information 10”, 1971, pg 28.

⁴ Cf. Frederic Jameson, “Euphoria and Self-Anihilation” in “Postmodernism, or the Cultural Logic of Late Capitalism”.

they differ radically in their relative positioning with respect current forces of production, thereby showing the paradigm shift . While Tafuri unfolds a criticality based upon resistance and the concept of alternative, Koolhaas proposes escalation⁵ and “aggressive exploration” of the new freedoms granted by contemporary society.

Thus, Tafuri and Koolhaas articulate two distinct reactions to the un-heroic and fully implemented modernity, while simultaneously trying to construct a critical thought. Alternative-resistance on the one hand, and escalation-reorientation on the other provide the framework for two modes of criticality within the regime of total modernity.

MARGINS

The question of marginality belongs to the problem of relevancy of action within the post-modern society. If prior to World War II, being modern meant “being other”, meant to occupy the margins of a yet limited modernity, after World War II, being modern means “being same”. Modernity, by virtue of its total implementation, has become the default condition, and has thus annihilated its margins. Both alternative and resistance are thus undermined. The very concept of alternative lies completely within Modernity as a project⁶, as it is yet another plan to be implemented through *enraisonnement*⁷, in a world that is understood as a mere silent site supporting a number of realities primarily devised through reason. Resistance (in its strict sense), is condemned to the framework constructed by that which it is resisting. Resistance is necessarily a negative mode of operating in the sense that accepts the problems as posed by the framework it is resisting, and thus, ultimately appears as reducible to it: i.e. resistance is unable to open up new horizons of sense, new modes of relevant action.

True marginality has disappeared, or, for that matter, it has lost its overturning power: marginality is currently being continuously re-appropriated as the very legitimization of the overall system. In such a setting, the question of criticality must be radically re-thought, as it can no longer rely on the marginal position of the revolutionary or the *maudit*.

SKYSCRAPER

“In the John Hancock Building, for instance, people can live, work, and participate in social life without ever leaving the gigantic antiurban mechanism.

This, indeed, is the real substance of these inventions, in spite of their intended aim of serving as eloquent symbols of the metropolis and its dynamics.”

Manfredo Tafuri , “The Disenchanted Mountain”, in “The American City”, pg 503.

“(…) the proliferation of floor space called Skyscraper.”

Rem Koolhaas, “Delirious New York”, pg 82.

Tafuri and Koolhaas’ points of view are articulated through the skyscraper, understood by both authors as a primordial product of the metropolitan condition. Meaningfully enough, their respective quasi-definitions of the skyscraper are quite revealing. While Tafuri intends to reveal the true nature of the skyscraper as a product of capitalism’s irrational drive for profit, and its ultimately evil outcomes, Koolhaas account, without denying the profit drive as a main issue in the

⁵ Escalation in the non-progressive understanding that Baudrillard articulates in his fatal figures (cf. Jean Baudrillard, “Las estrategias fatales”, Anagrama, Barcelona). What such proliferative escalation produces, rather than an intensification of the qualities or characteristics, is a brisk swerve when a certain critical point is reached. Such swerve displaces the very characteristics of the original figure (or problem, situation) to found a new horizon that can no longer be accounted for as an mere intensification of the former.

⁶ When we refer to Modernity, we are referring to Modernity strictu sensu (i.e. starting with Descartes and virtually settled with Kant), rather than early 20th century Modernism .

⁷ French term referring to (western post-Cartesian) reason’s effacing character : reason as the plough that radically reshapes the field, engraving an overall pattern in the whole surface. Concepts so dear to modernity as *tabula rasa* or alternative (be it under the form of Communism or under that of Hippism) are only thinkable within such paradigm.

history of the skyscraper, takes on a very different hue. Koolhaas expands capitalist greed into the realm of the fantastic⁸, ultimately opening into the skyscraper's subversive "true nature": the "ultimate unpredictability of its performance". For Koolhaas, thus, capitalist greed for profit is definitely there, but as an alibi rather than as a driving end in itself. Tafuri, on the contrary, tends to understand capitalist greed as the very nature of the skyscraper, it being a "direct expression of the forces of production".

Where Tafuri focuses on the readable character of the skyscraper as a cultural product, striving to understand the cultural framework where it appeared, Koolhaas focuses on the proliferational character of the skyscraper, striving to derive from it modes of operation relevant for contemporary architectural practice.

POST-HUMANISM AND ECOLOGICAL THOUGHT

"New York is ugly as a city, it has to be regarded as a geological formation."

Claude Levi-Strauss

While Tafuri insists in understanding the city as the (ultimate and exclusive) cultural construction of mankind, Koolhaas allows for structures of explanation other than humanity to subsist in his account of Manhattan.

The post-humanist shift experienced by post-structuralist philosophy⁹ is made clear in here. That constitutes a very significant difference between the critical platforms constructed by both authors, having direct implications with the already cited change of paradigm.

Ecological thought as articulated by Paul Virilio and Manuel De Landa among many others, seems to be a good example of post-humanist thought in operation. Ecological thought (not *ecologism* particularly) models a framework of operational procedures where Carbon-based organic life itself is a particular case of a much larger self-sustaining dynamical system¹⁰. The metropolis, thus, is understood as a meshwork of systems, including cultural, biological, and geological processes, related to each other but at the same time irreducible.

In Koolhaas, this "antropofugical" move is obvious, among other issues in his treatment of bigness (critical mass), of cultural landscape's own inertias, and capital accumulation's intrinsic logic. All of these issues undermine human (exclusive) authorship of the metropolis, and ultimately humanity's ability to control it.

⁸ "the man-made territories of the frontier of the sky could be settled by the Irresistible Synthetic to establish alternative realities on any level". Koolhaas, op. cit pg 87.

⁹ "(...) the themes addressed and transgressed in French postmodernism an post-structuralism: (...) the concept of the "disappearance of man" and the simultaneous disappearance of history as a Hegelian-Marxist project, and thus the disappearance of the project of modernity." Julian Pefanis, "Heterology and the Postmodern", Duke University Press 1991, pg 2.

"One can even say that, from a certain point of view, the United States has attained the final stage of Marxist "communism". ...I was led to conclude that the "American way of life" was the type of life specific to the post-historical period, the actual presence of the United States in the world prefiguring the "eternal present" future of all humanity." Alexandre Kojève, "Introduction to the Reading of Hegel's Phenomenology of Mind", pg 160.

¹⁰ Cf. Manuel De Landa, "A thousand years of non-linear history", Swerve Editions, New York 1997. De Landa accounts for particular organizations in fields as apparently disconnected as geology, biology and culture through the same abstract machines, i.e. lava, gene and word are accounted for from a consistent operational framework:

"I have argued that structures as different as sedimentary rocks, animal species, and social classes may be viewed as historical products of the same structure-generating processes. (Or more accurately, of different concrete processes embodying the same abstract machine or engineering diagram)." pg 215

"(...) in a non-linear world in which the same basic processes of self-organization take place in the mineral, organic, and cultural spheres, perhaps rocks hold some of the keys to understanding sedimentary humanity, igneous humanity, and all their mixtures." pg 70.

THE ISSUE OF SIZE

"The organic quality of his design [Saarinen's 1922 Chicago Tribune competition entry] was to be interpreted as the victory of architecture over the artificiality of the metropolis. (...) For Sullivan, the mind of man had here succeeded in expressing itself in designing an object in which gigantic size was not antithetical to the organic ideal."

Manfredo Tafuri, "The Disenchanted Mountain", in "The American City", pp 417-418.

"Beyond a certain critical mass each structure becomes a monument (...) This category of monument presents a radical, morally traumatic break with the conventions of symbolism: (...) it merely is itself [a monument] and through sheer volume cannot avoid being a symbol –an empty one, available for meaning as a billboard is for advertisement."

Rem Koolhaas, "Delirious New York", pg 100.

"Everything can be sacrificed to the metaphysics of quantity they [super-skyscrapers] incarnate."
Manfredo Tafuri, "The Disenchanted Mountain", in "The American City", pg 500

"Beyond a certain scale, architecture acquires the properties of Bigness.(...) It seems incredible that the size of a building alone embodies an ideological programme, independent of the will of its architects (...) only Bigness instigates the regime of complexity that mobilizes the full intelligence of architecture and its related fields."

Rem Koolhaas, "Bigness or the problem of Large" in "S,M,L,XL" pp 495-497.

The problem of "a larger *mass* than ever constructed before" underlies the history of the skyscraper. As we have already pointed out, Koolhaas' take on that issue is especially interesting insofar it stages matter itself as an active part in the negotiating of the metropolis, beyond any human attempt to control it. The proliferative character of mass accumulation imposes its own logic and its own inertia within the urban condition, drastically reorganizing it. Tafuri's understanding of the skyscraper's large mass accumulation, conversely, reduces mass to immobilized capital¹¹, and, furthermore, he draws negative social implications of such accumulation through the loss of the public realm.

According to Tafuri, "antiurbanity" is the real substance of the skyscraper. The "gigantic antiurban machine"¹², thus, appears as a threat to (conventional) public realm, an obstructing mechanism further escalating the ladder of alienation. The metropolis, understood as the seat of power insofar the setting of capital accumulation, is revealed as well as the "scene (...) where all the alienation of modern life becomes evident in physical form"¹³. In Koolhaas, nevertheless, the anti-urban outcome of the skyscraper is played out in a thoroughly different way, exploring the horizon of new freedoms it opens up, rather than crying out the losses it entails. Public realm shifts from the traditional community-based identity-reinforcing framework, to an unprecedented horizon constituted by an endless number of combinations of the most disparate activities. Every "house" (huge virtual skyscraper occupying a whole block), or even every floor, represents and enacts an alternative reality, a "different lifestyle and a different ideology"¹⁴, reproducible wherever and whenever desired.

¹¹ Cf. "The Evolution of Skyscrapers", film produced by Francis Thompson in the 1930's, where a group of piles of coins is directly translated (optically) as downtown Manhattan built bulk: the higher the pile of coins, the higher the building.

¹² Manfredo Tafuri, op. cit., pg 503.

¹³ Stan Allen, from the present essay's Final Take-Home Exam sheet, question number one.

¹⁴ Koolhaas, op. cit. pg 125.

CONGESTION

"4) *The degree of light and access to outer air that is necessary in buildings for health is also economically desirable, as it is one of the best means of maintaining property values.*"

Thomas Adams, "Regional Survey", 1931, quoted from Tafuri op. cit., pg 439.

"What is of greater interest [in Raymond Hood's proposal for the "City under a Single Roof" skyscraper type], however, is the centralization of residence and place of work in a single structure. This was an anticipation of the super-skyscrapers of the 1960's and 1970's, but with one difference –Hood theorized an almost complete reconstruction of Manhattan on the basis of his model, to be carried out within about twenty years. This hypertrophic concentration, which would eliminate not only the phenomenon of commuting but also the drama of congestion, was valid only if New York could be transformed into a ville radieuse."

Manfredo Tafuri, "The Disenchanted Mountain", in "The American City", pg 440

"Ferriss, Corbett, and the authors of the Regional Plan have invented a method to deal rationally with the fundamentally irrational.

They know instinctively that it would be suicide to solve Manhattan's problems, that they exist by grace of these problems, that it is their duty to make these problems, if anything, forever insurmountable, that the only solution for Manhattan is the extrapolation of its freakish history, that Manhattan is the city of the perpetual flight forward."

Rem Koolhaas, "Delirious New York", pg 123.

The culture of congestion, staging the performative aspects of density, has been widely accepted as a keystone of modern metropolitan condition, both its product and milieu in an ever-increasing autocatalytic loop. Once again, in Tafuri and Koolhaas' respective accounts of congestion, their similitude and differences surface. Koolhaas welcomes the fundamental irrationality of the culture of congestion, "*the culture of the 20th century*"¹⁵, where rationality plays an instrumental role. The acknowledgement of the fundamentally irrational character of capitalism is used as strategic knowledge to build a platform of critical thought and, above all, action. Tafuri, on the other hand, tries to oppose it a rational alternative (ultimately, a totalizing horizon), whereby density (and not congestion so much) would have beneficial social effects by virtue of its configuration as public realm. Public realm thus conceived acts in two main directions: as a tool for (class) consciousness, and as a scenario for emancipation. Both directions aim at unveiling the fundamental condition of modern man: alienation. Needless to say, the paradigm of alienation implies the existence of a non-alienated, emancipated state, where men would be in a state of utter conscience, and aims at such state.

TO OVERTURN REALITY – TO NAVIGATE REALITY

While Tafuri operates from oppositions, opposing alternative realities (necessarily rational and often totalizing, insofar as they are abstract plans to be implemented), Koolhaas cannot but reorient a multiform and fundamentally irrational reality, his aim being less to fully comprehend reality but to engage with it through relevant practice¹⁶.

Tafuri ultimately intends to overturn reality through the rational expose of its mystifying character in the form of a *grand récit*.

Koolhaas navigates reality from the recognition of *plateaux of temporary stabilities*, endlessly deferred by the proliferational character of reality.

¹⁵ Koolhaas, op.cit. pg 125.

¹⁶ Relevancy, of course, is defined precisely by such engagement, by the degree of consistency achieved by the friction of action (performance) and that we call reality.

HISTORY

However diverging, both Tafuri and Koolhaas build up a history of the skyscraper. Even more pertinent than their very accounts of the skyscraper is the notion of history they articulate.

In Tafuri, history is a *grand recit*, rationally unfolding. The obvious irrationalities of our ways to understand and manage reality, are to be revealed, ultimately, as mystifications of capitalism. This totalizing approach to the temporality of history, uses mainly the traditional dichotomy of synchronic and diachronic analysis of events.

Koolhaas, on the other hand, understands and uses history as a toolbox. His performative use of history differs greatly from that of what has come to be known as “semiotic post-modernity”. Koolhaas does not see history as a huge catalogue of legitimized solutions with a supposedly indisputable meaning attached by virtue of the historical process that actually produced them. His operating within history as a manageable platform seems to play out Walter Benjamin’s “feeble redemptive power”¹⁷, by virtue of which each generation has a (limited) power to redeem the past, and the past itself has a right to that redemption. Ultimately, history is the framework by virtue of which a given number of pasts (and *not* others) become relevant to a given present –and most importantly, they exist only insofar as they are made relevant by a particular present. Each present remakes its own history, and it is through the pasts it chooses to receive that it defines itself in relationship with broader history. Koolhaas’ history of the skyscraper, as opposed to Tafuri’s, is actually not a history in the traditional sense of an ordered account of events that captures a past, but rather the building of a platform for contemporary practice. The past Koolhaas chooses to investigate becomes his history of modern architecture, the genealogy that frames his own work as a practicing architect in the end of the century. Through his current work, Koolhaas redeems a certain past, establishing a connection that cannot be reduced to synchronicity or diachronicity. Such approach, or relationship should we say, to temporality, we call *transchronicity*¹⁸.

The very idea of a “retroactive manifesto”¹⁹ is only understandable within such a conception of history.

The different notion of history articulated by each author is played out not only in the ideas conveyed by the text, but in the very style²⁰ of the text and in the horizons that these diverging conceptions implicate. The chronological and taxonomical account of the skyscraper in Tafuri differs greatly from Koolhaas’ fairly chronological but nevertheless “constellation-like” account. Tafuri unfolds a totalizing logic evenly across the historical and cultural material he covers, while Koolhaas uses this very material to construct concepts, concepts that are relevant to contemporary architectural practice. Rather than trying to comprehensively explain history, Koolhaas uses history as a raw, live material²¹.

Ultimately, what it is here at play is a different appropriation of facts: Tafuri uses facts as legitimization of an overarching narrative, as proofs to a statement or contention that ultimately aspires to explain reality. Koolhaas, conversely, uses facts to detonate or catalyze further proliferations of reality.

¹⁷ Cf. Walter Benjamin, “Tesis de Filosofía de la Historia”, in “Walter Benjamin, Art i Ciutat”, Barcelona 1995.

¹⁸ *Transchronic* is a neologism somehow informed by both “transgressive” and “transversal”. It implies an *active* relationship with history, and a non-linear temporality that compels one to face the constructed character of (any) history as well as the non-metaphorical presence of (a number of) pasts. Lina Bo Bardi’s statement gathers some of that *transchronic* character of time:

“But time is not linear. Linear time is an invention of the west. Time is a wonderful tangle where, at any given time, points can be chosen, and relationships established.”

¹⁹ “Delirious New York: A Retroactive Manifesto for Manhattan”.

²⁰ We use “style” along the lines of Deleuze. Cf. Gilles Deleuze, about bird songs in “A Thousand Plateaux”.

²¹ Cf. Walter Benjamin, *op. cit.* (thesis number XIV) : “History is the object of a construction the *locus* of which does not constitute homogeneous and void time, but time constituted of a *Jetztzeit*. [now-time]” Approximate translation from Catalan.

(Any given) present is full, is a time of “possibilities and action”. *Jetztzeit*, or the now as time rather than the now as instant, sets itself up as humanized time opposed to the de-humanized time of progress as articulated by modernity.

OUTRO:

THE PROBLEM OF RELEVANT ACTION IN CONTEMPORARY ARCHITECTURAL PRACTICE

“these multiform, tricky and stubborn procedures that elude discipline without being outside the field in which it is exercised, and which should lead us to a theory (...) of the disquieting familiarity of the city.”

Michel de Certeau²²

The double play we tried to establish between Tafuri and Koolhaas' respective histories of the skyscraper does not intend to set itself up as a scholarly study, but rather it aims at hinting a consistent framework for contemporary architectural practice.

The following paragraphs try to point out some of the virtually relevant issues for contemporary architectural practice, directly or indirectly touched upon in the play we have just staged.

MEANING

Resituating of the problem of meaning: performative and operational factors appear as more important than symbolic or communicational interests derived from a linguistic understanding of architecture. This shift favours, after all, a political understanding (and enacting of) architecture to the detriment of a high culture²³ approach. The separation from the problem of meaning proper, enacts an obstruction of the problem of translation in favour of that of consistency. The obstruction of translation, rather than solving most of the problems posed by post-modernity's reaction to the perceived crisis of meaning, deems them irrelevant²⁴. Such regard implies a re-considering of the role that disciplines extraneous to architecture must play. Rather than reducing architecture to a sheer illustrator, reducing its role to celebrating if not monumentalizing other disciplines' insights²⁵, architecture can engage such disciplines re-orientating architecture itself, from its operational parameters to its methods of validation and legitimization. Rather than using those external inputs as a legitimization²⁶, contemporary practice may truly incorporate their mode of operating, even if that entails the disappearance of architecture, and the figure of the architect, as we know it. Consistency appears as an appropriate framework for meaning, where meaning has lost its linguistic attributes in favour of performative ones. Consistency, in the form of intense coherence²⁷, displaces high-modernist totalizing wholes without aestheticizing reality's fragmented character, allowing for an architecture that engenders heterogeneity while resisting to fit into fixed hierarchies, seeking to “contribute to a non-hierarchical, heterogeneous political space”²⁸.

CRITIQUE

Retreat from barricade positions of resistance²⁹ to engage with the actual forces shaping the world, through reorientation³⁰. The disappearance of marginality through re-appropriation by a virtually globally implemented modernity cannot be cried out as a fundamental loss. Rather, in a post-historical setting, the whole notion of critique must be rethought to allow for its (relevant) existence. The post-modern accounts of the end of history frame contemporary criticality. While Kojève's account of Hegel's end of history³¹ was behind some of the most remarkable outbreak

²² Cf. Michel de Certeau, “The Practice of Everyday Life”, University of California Press, 1984, pg 96.

²³ Or low-culture as theorized by high culture, for that matter.

²⁴ Or, in any case, not so central.

²⁵ Currently, mainly literature, biology, philosophy, mathematics, and sociology. Cf. For example, a recent invention such as “folded architecture” claiming to be an offspring of Deleuze's *pli*.

²⁶ Ultimately formal and social legitimization, *social* in the sense of the architect's hierarchical position within society.

²⁷ Cf. Jeff Kipnis, “Towards a New Architecture” : “ (...) a coherence forged out of incongruity. Intensive coherence implies that the properties of certain monolithic arrangements enable the architecture to enter into multiple and even contradictory relationships.”

²⁸ *Id.*

²⁹ We are referring to resistance in its more strict sense, not to denote those “stubborn procedures that elude discipline”.

³⁰ To put it in Koolhaas words, “to ride the Zeitgeist as the surfer rides the waves”.

³¹ Cf. Julian Pefanis, *op. cit.*, pp 2 (Kojève's quote especially) and 9.

of critical thought (namely Sartre, Merleau-Ponty, Lacan, Bataille, Queneau, etc³²), some more recent takes on the same question (namely Fukuyama) ooze reactionary-ness and obstruct any space for criticality.

The divergence of the critical spaces opened up by architects such as Daniel Libeskind or Rem Koolhaas himself is quite representative of the contemporary situation. Libeskind's notion of critique, as staged in his work, strives to come to terms with contemporary condition through monumentalization, through supplying a cultural positioning of an already existing condition. Koolhaas' critique, however, is essentially transformative, it tries to understand contemporaneity to use its forces and inertias to transform the very framework in which those forces operate. What appears as most interesting of that position is the non-coincidence of (a) will with the framework, the preserving of will being probably at the very base of a truly powerful criticality. The fact that Koolhaas actually gets things done in an apparently refractory and over-determined framework, and the fact that he actually enacts a proliferation of architecture in the form of inventions (of something that just was not there before), shows that relevant architecture, beyond the polarization between the sophistication (of a neo-avant garde) and the total reduction to the framework of contemporary societies, can take place. Or, to put it in other words, constructing a criticality that uses the framework that it is criticizing rather than opposing it (as an ideological positioning), allows for relevant transformative action through reorientation, i.e. it opens up new horizons of sense and new modes of acting.

³² All of them students of Alexandre Kojève's influential course on Hegel's "Phenomenology of Mind".

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